

Recommended citation: Li, T., Wang, Y., Li, C., & Wu, W. (2019). A systematic literature review of China's new engineering education. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 1694-1720). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14657071.

A Systematic Literature Review of China New Engineering

Education

Li Tuoyu

(College of Public Affairs, Zhejiang University, Zhejiang Hangzhou, 310058)

Wang Yujie

(Corresponding Author, College of Public Affairs, Zhejiang University, Zhejiang Hangzhou, 310058, happypp@zju.edu.cn)

Li Chen

(Institute of China's Science, Technology and Education Policy, Zhejiang University, Zhejiang Hangzhou, 310058)

Wu Wei

(Institute of China's Science, Technology and Education Policy, Zhejiang University, Zhejiang Hangzhou, 310058)

Funding Information: Philosophy and Social Science Foundation of Zhejiang Province (CN) (19NDQN343YB)

ABSTRACT

With the advent of a new round of industrial revolution, China has put forward its New Engineering Education initiative at the right time. A literature review is an important way to understand the current state and future directions of New Engineering Education. The Systematic Literature Review is an internationally emerging and widely applicable research method that adopts standardized data coding technology, integrating systematic and qualitative evaluations to examine the literature on specific issues and formulate new problems and theories. This study provides an overview of research and practice in New Engineering Education in China by systematically analyzing articles containing the keyword “New Engineering Education.” These articles were published in the main journals of the CNKI database from January 2017, when the concept of “New Engineering” was first proposed. Two hundred and sixty studies were analyzed with 6 first-level codes and more than 20 second-level codes. After presenting the results of the analysis, three cases are described in detail in terms of the specific paths in practice from technical universities, comprehensive universities, and regional universities. The results showed that New Engineering Education resulted from the joint promotion of multiple levels and subjects and that its construction logic could be classified into policy logic, industrial logic, disciplinary logic, and the logic of knowledge. By integrating these different types of logic, this study constructed a systematic analysis framework for research and practice in New Engineering Education. As a result, this study helps to explain how engineering education has evolved in the face of the Fourth Industrial Revolution and market demand and facilitates efforts to find a possible breakthrough to promote a paradigm shift in engineering education.

Keywords

New Engineering Education; Content Analysis; Logic Exploration; Systematic Review

Introduction

With the progressive of cutting-edge technologies such as artificial intelligence, big data, and cloud computing, a new round of scientific and technological revolution and industrial revolution led by intelligent industry has emerged. The manufacturing industry has once again become a key point of global economic competition. Countries have formulated manufacturing development strategies to revitalize their manufacturing industry. It can be predicted that in the next 20 years, the “new format” of engineering in the context of technological and industrial change will offer new opportunities and new challenges for the reform and development of engineering education around the world. Universities around the world have launched corresponding reform plans, such as the NEET Plan (2017-2020) proposed by MIT; the second phase of the Excellence Initiative proposed by RWTH Aachen University in 2012; RWTH 2020: Meeting Global Challenges—The Integrated Interdisciplinary University of Technology; and the Comprehensive Engineering Plan launched by University College London in September 2014. At the right time, the Ministry of Education of China has put forward the “New Engineering Education” plan, setting the direction of China’s engineering education reform in light of the new situation of international competition, the new demand for national strategic development, and the new requirement to cultivate talent. This plan offers a positive response to major national strategies, such as Internet Plus, Made in China 2025, and The Belt and Road Initiative.

Since the Ministry of Education proposed New Engineering Education (NEE) in February 2017, research and practice in New Engineering Education have become focuses of attention from all walks of life. As a result, a large number of theoretical and empirical studies on this topic have sprung up like mushrooms in the recent two years. Through bibliometric analysis, we found that the number of relevant studies in New Engineering Education has increased significantly since 2017 and that the number of research papers on New Engineering Education in each quarter has almost increased significantly compared with the previous quarter (see Figure 1). In terms of research methods, most studies have followed the tradition of research in engineering education, discussing the construction status and corresponding connotation characteristics of New Engineering Education based on typical cases using case study methods(Lu & Shang Guan, 2018; Qin &Wang, 2018; Yang &Yu, 2019). A small number of studies have explored the factors influencing the participation of engineering students in science and technology competitions based on large-scale questionnaire surveys (Mao &Dai, 2019), the quality of professional construction in New Engineering Education based on the process factor model(Liu,Xiong,&Zhang, 2019), and the development of

engineering education in China over the last 40 years (see Figure 2). In terms of academic journals, *Education Modernization*, *Education and Teaching Forum*, and *Research in Higher Education of Engineering* have become the leading academic publishing platforms in New Engineering Education.

Figure1: Quarterly Changes in NEE

Figure2: Distribution by Category of NEE

The current literature on research and practice in New Engineering Education has focused on explaining the integration and externality of engineering education but ignored the logicity of disciplinary evolution and knowledge derivation, which has led to great limitations in explaining the evolution of New Engineering Education. It is therefore necessary to carry out systematic coding and structural analysis of previous studies. Based on a detailed discussion of specific paths for the development of New Engineering Education in different types of colleges and universities, this study attempts to construct a systematic analysis framework for research and practice in New Engineering Education to explain how engineering education has evolved in the face of the Fourth Industrial Revolution and market demand and to find a possible breakthrough to promote the paradigm shift in engineering education. To this end, this study carries out a systematic coded and structured review of 260 documents published in the main CNKI journals with the keyword “New Engineering Education,” since the emergence of the concept in January 2017. Starting by exploring the motivations behind the development of New Engineering Education based on the context of this development, it then refines subject characteristics, talent training objectives, construction situations, and other elements and explores its underlying logic.

Methodology

This study used a Systematic Literature Review (Jesson, Matheson, & Lacey, 2011; Borrego, Foster, & Froyd, 2014) method to systematically review and analyze the New Engineering Education literature from January 2017 to June 2019. The systematic review included a content analysis, which was conducive to the critical evaluation and synthesis of previous findings, and provided useful information for future practice in research (Borrego et al., 2014). Borrego et al. (2014) proposed key steps to follow in a systematic literature review: (a) deciding to conduct a review, (b) identifying the scope of research and research questions, (c) defining the inclusion criteria, (d) identifying and cataloging the sources, (e) criticizing and evaluating these sources, and (f) synthesizing the results. Based on this method, this study adjusted and expanded these key steps as follows.

Defining: Research Questions and Sub-questions

This study systematically reviewed the literature on New Engineering Education, sorted and commented on the results of current research in New Engineering Education, and integrated logical relationships to construct a systematic analysis framework to analyze the development of New Engineering Education. What was the logic and path of its development? To answer this question, this study further defined the following key points: (1) Why was New Engineering Education developed? (2) Who developed it? (3) What kind of people should New Engineering Education cultivate? (4) At what level (and where) was New Engineering Education developed? (5) How can New Engineering Education be developed?

Scoping: Identify Where and How to Search the Literature

Using the keyword “New Engineering Education,” all documents from January 1, 2017 to June 30, 2019 were searched in the China National Knowledge Infrastructure (CNKI). After eliminating duplicates, 1,932 articles were collected.

Coding: Collect the literature and develop a coding framework

First, after removing non-academic articles from newspapers and conference papers/abstracts, 1,838 valid documents were eliminated through preliminary screening, removing duplicates, and deleting erroneous messages. It is obvious that although New Engineering Education was proposed only two years ago, it has always been a popular topic. Therefore, to ensure the authority and effectiveness of the articles, only the journals from CSSCI and those of Peking University's main journal catalogs were retained. The remaining articles were re-examined and all duplicates and errors were eliminated, resulting in a final sample of 260 valid articles. Each data entry included 9 elements of bibliographic information about the article: title, Chinese keywords, author, organization, affiliated funding, journal name, year, period, and abstract in Chinese (Table 1).

Table 1 Overview of the coding framework

Category	Item	Category	Item
Authors	The first author	Region of the first author	Anhui
	The second author		Zhejiang

Journals	Research in Higher Education of Engineering	Quarter	First quarter
	China University Teaching		Second quarter
	Education Modernization		Third quarter
Research Methods	Case study	Research Content	Motivation
	Normative study		Subject
	Interview		Objective
	Empirical study		Situation

Source: Compiled by the author

Checking: Inter-rater Reliability

Reliability in content analysis emphasizes the consistency, stability, and reliability of the measurement results of the analysis dimensions. Internal consistency results mainly from the degree of consistency of two authors coding the same content. To improve the reliability of content coding, the researchers adopted the basic process of coder training, double-blind evaluation, negotiation of differences, and mutual recognition. In the pretest, the researchers performed a preliminary reliability test on the coded content. First, the two content raters were invited and trained in coding. The training included understanding the coding table, mastering the coding procedures, and using coding tools skillfully. Next, the raters conducted a double-blind evaluation and discussed and resolved any inconsistencies.

Analysis

Motivations for the Development of New Engineering Education

Based on the literature review, this study classified these motivations into three categories: format change, national strategy, and paradigm shift in engineering education (see Table 2).

Table 2 Content of Research on Development Motivations for NEE

Motivation	Typical Description
Format change	With new advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence, big data, and cloud computing, to make breakthroughs in technology, the “new format” will introduce new subversive features in the future: Humanity, Technology, Scale, Polity, or Industry.
National strategy	With the rapid development of the new scientific and technological revolution and the new industrial revolution, competition in comprehensive national power has become increasingly fierce. We must find solutions through innovation. Major strategies include Innovation-driven Development, Made in China 2025, Internet Plus, Cyber Power, and The Belt and Road Initiative.
Paradigm shift in engineering education	Slogans such as “Return to Engineering”, “Paradigm Shift in Engineering Education” and “Reengineering Education” were proposed.

Source: Based on studies by Ye et al. (2018), Xu et al. (2017), and Wang (2013), among others.

First, the global industrial transformation has led to the development of New Engineering Education. Engineering education and industrial development are closely linked and mutually supportive. Indeed, the development of new formats relies on engineering education to provide new talent. Therefore, efficiently developing the active layout and deepening the reform of engineering education can promote the vigorous development of a new economy characterized by new technologies, new formats, new industries, and new modes, and can foster economic transformation and upgrading. Only when New Engineering Education is able to break through key technologies will China be able to gain first-mover advantage and occupy the strategic commanding heights of future global innovation ecosystems (Hu et al., 2017). From this perspective, the talent knowledge structure of the “new format” posed new challenges, forcing engineering talent to take into account both sound professional technology and compound knowledge. Therefore, the development of New Engineering Education was necessary for the transformation of global formats. Second, the development of national strategies led to the development of New Engineering Education. With the rapid development of the new scientific and technological revolution and the new industrial revolution, competition in comprehensive national power has become increasingly fierce (Xu et al., 2017). It was therefore necessary to find a solution through innovation. The historical experience of developed countries has shown that the active adjustment of the structure of higher education and the development of new frontier disciplines are the central elements to promote the structural transformation of national and regional human capital and achieve the transformation from a traditional economy to a new economy. China has implemented a number of major strategies, such as Innovation-driven Development, Made in China 2025, Internet Plus, Cyber Power, and The Belt and Road Initiative. To respond to the country’s strategic needs, support the vigorous development of a new economy characterized by new formats, break through key technologies, gain first-

mover advantage, and occupy the strategic commanding heights of global innovation ecosystems in the future, it was necessary to rapidly cultivate a large number of emerging talents in engineering and science with increased capacity for innovation, change, and adaptability(Xu et al., 2017; Zhong, 2017). Therefore, the New Engineering Education initiative was a positive response to China’s major strategies. It also illustrated the concept of “China’s experience” and “China’s model” in engineering education(Wu et al., 2017).Its purpose was to cultivate talent that could adapt and even drive future engineering needs(Li, 2017), meet the main needs of the country, industry, and science and technology(Hu et al., 2017), improve the country’s future competitiveness, and win competitions in the global market(Lu& Li, 2017). Third, the paradigm shift in engineering education has led to the development of New Engineering Education. From the perspective of global engineering education paradigm reform, engineering education is represented on the axis of science and technology, namely the period of the technological paradigm, that of the scientific paradigm, and that of the engineering paradigm. At the end of the 20th century, international engineering education reform was developing. The slogans “Return to Engineering” (Wang, 2013), “Paradigm shift in Engineering Education” and “Reengineering Education” were proposed, reflecting the trend of international development of innovative engineering education (see Figure 3). The engineering paradigm belongs to the paradigm of integrating science and technology(Wall, 2010), and its practical tasks include project organization and communication. This paradigm highlights the role of students as professional consultants, their innovative design capabilities and empirical requirements, and ethical issues related to how science can be applied in society(Li, 2010).

Figure 3: Theoretical Basis of the Engineering Education System. Source: Drawn by the author.

In summary, the New Engineering Education initiative was a Chinese practice aimed at actively adapting to the global trend of engineering education. Based on the perspective of the dynamic development of engineering(Reynolds & Seely, 1993), scholars have proposed that engineering education has undergone continuous development(Lin, 2017; Wang, 2017; Wu et al., 2017; Xu& Ding, 2017).Indeed, New Engineering Education was based not only on the creation of new disciplines and new specialties in the process of knowledge discovery, but also on the upgrading and transformation of traditional industries and old specialties(Li, Hu & You, 2017; Wang, 2017; Wu et al., 2017). The proposal for New Engineering Education was essential to reform the paradigm of engineering education with Chinese characteristics, to regain the central position of the “Engineering Paradigm” in engineering education, to clarify the guiding role of the system paradigm in all engineering education practices, and to solve the problems of “training concept, talent structure, knowledge system, training mode” and other problems of maladaptation of talent training in engineering education in China (Zhong, 2017).

Subjects of the Development of New Engineering Education

To explore the Chinese path and mode of the development of New Engineering Education, we must understand the developmental characteristics of higher education in the new era based on the current situation of higher education in China, starting with the subject of the development of New Engineering Education: how to combine the characteristics and advantages of different types of universities to carry out the essential work of New Engineering Education. In the only case study of domestic colleges and universities, the research momentum of Regional Universities was rapid(74articles), surpassing the sum of articles based on Comprehensive Universities and Technical Universities(see Table 3). This result highlighted the enthusiasm of Regional Universities to participate in the development of New Engineering Education.

Table 3 Content of Research on the Development of New Engineering Education

Subject	Characteristics	Cases	Main content
Technical Universities	Overall strength in engineering, benefits of research and development in technology, and close relationships with industries	Zhejiang University, Xi'an Jiaotong University, Shanghai Jiaotong University	Actively optimized the layout of disciplines and specialties, broadened the connotation and focus of engineering specialties, and fully exploited the key benefits of engineering in response to the urgent needs of current and future industrial development
Comprehensive Universities	Multidisciplinary, strong basic discipline and scientific research, and diversity in resource allocation	Fudan University, Sun Yat-sen University, the University of Science and Technology of China	Promoted the extension of applied science to engineering, explored the development path of New Engineering Education, grasped the concept of overall school development, and appropriately adjusted their system
Regional Universities	Focused on the region, relied on local resources for support, fully exploited the benefits of integrating production and education	Shanghai University of Engineering Science, Wenzhou University	Focused on a regional mode of economic development and industrial transformation and upgrading, and deepened the creation of an interactive development between engineering education and the economic society

Source: Based on studies by Lu et al. (2017), Lin (2017), Bao et al. (2017), Xu et al. (2017), Chen et al. (2017) and Xu et al. (2017).

Based on current research, the three types of colleges and universities involved in New Engineering Education had different characteristics and advantages, and their main content and directions were also emphasized. This study performed a structural analysis of this result. It found that Technical Universities relied on the overall strength of engineering, the benefits of research and development in technology, and close relationships with the industry. They actively optimized the layout of disciplines and specialties, broadened the connotation and focus of engineering specialties, and fully exploited the key benefits of engineering in response to the urgent needs of current and future industrial development. In contrast, Comprehensive Universities had the following characteristics: multidisciplinary, sound basic disciplines and scientific research, and diversity in resource allocation. They actively promoted the extension of applied science to engineering, explored the development path of New Engineering Education, grasped the concept of overall school development, and appropriately adjusted their system. Finally, Regional Universities mainly focused on the region, relied on the support of local resources, fully exploited the benefits of integrating production and education, adopted a regional mode of economic development and industrial transformation and upgrading, and deepened the creation of an interactive development between engineering education and the economic society.

As the subjects of the development of New Engineering Education, the unique attributes of colleges and universities determined the objectives and paths of development. However, during the development of New Engineering Education, the traditional advantages of some colleges and universities were not fully exploited, the convergence of construction ideas and practices was obvious, and there was a lack of systematic construction layout. Clearly, it is not possible to fully stimulate internal motivations for the development of New Engineering Education simply by adding to the curriculum and developing professional joint training and industrial docking. Therefore, in the process of developing New Engineering Education, problems such as the unclear orientation of engineering talent training, the scientization of engineering teaching, and the gap between engineering education and industrial enterprises should be avoided (Xu,Wang,&Shi, 2017), while more systematic and overall methods and measures should be adopted. By combining the characteristics and attributes of colleges and universities, attention should be paid to the development of sub-regional distribution, the management and construction of classification, the reform of talent training mechanisms, and the optimization of engineering education evaluation systems (Chen&Chen, 2017).

Objectives of the Development of New Engineering Education

In accordance with the rules of interaction between global higher education and previous industrial revolutions, and new trends and new requirements for the future development of technology and industry(MOE, 2017), scholars have focused on two main objectives in the development of New Engineering Education based on the experience of the technological paradigm, the scientific paradigm, and the engineering paradigm: discipline development and capability structure.

Discipline Development

The new technological revolution and the new industrial revolution have created a new format for global development. In addition, the development of the global economy has generated new requirements for engineering education. Through classification, we found that the popular topics and keywords covered in the “new format” involved “sharing” (Lu, 2017; Zhu,Zhou,&Li, 2017), “inoscultation” (Lin, 2017; Zhu,Zhou,&Li, 2017), “integration” (Zhu,Zhou,&Li, 2017), “innovation” (Zhong, 2017), and “intelligence” (Zhu,Zhou,&Li, 2017).Based on current research, the development of New Engineering Education was based on the law of dynamic evolution of the discipline itself against the backdrop of the new economy and new industries, offering a certain degree of autonomy and flexibility(Lin&Hu, 2018)to meet the new requirements for the development of disciplines under the “new format”. This included three aspects. First, a number of emerging engineering disciplines were established (Wu et al., 2017). Second, promoting the reform and innovation of the current engineering specialty, a new discipline developed from the transformation and upgrading of traditional engineering (Huanget al., 2019). Third, this new discipline was generated by the cross-combination of different engineering disciplines or the cross-integration of engineering disciplines and other disciplines (Li et al., 2019; Lin, 2017b).

Capacity structure

The development of New Engineering Education focused on “leading-edge technology”, “diversity of knowledge systems” and “innovation in talent cultivation” (Ye,Kong,&Zhang, 2018). It was necessary to cultivate engineering talent that could adapt and even meet future engineering needs(Li, 2017)in response to the new requirements of the new industrial revolution and the scientific and technological revolution (Wuet al., 2017). The key to cultivating such talent was to study the talent capacity structure of New Engineering Education. General Secretary Xi Jinping proposed at the National Education Conference in 2018 “to provide socialist builders and successors with all-round development in morality, intelligence, physique, art and labor.”¹As a result, current research has further

¹ <http://edu.people.com.cn/n1/2018/0911/c1053-30286253.html>

explored the talent capacity structure of New Engineering Education (see Table 4) in combination with the development characteristics of new technologies, new industries, and the new economy. In this study, it was systematically divided into five aspects. The first aspect, the spirit of engineering ethics, emphasized technical ethics, ethical interests, and the ethical responsibility of engineering. As engineering ethics problems often originated in engineering practice, it was necessary to explore them in the process of talent training (Lin, 2018). The second aspect, professional basic ability, emphasized having strong professional basic knowledge, skills, and abilities (Xu & Ding, 2017). The third aspect, sustainable competitiveness, emphasized that students should have the knowledge, quality, and ability to recognize changes in the process of social informatization, the role of science and engineering in promoting these changes, and their effects on globalization (Wall, 2010). The fourth aspect, innovative design capacity (Lu, 2017; Ye, Kong, & Zhang, 2018), focused on developing the capacity for innovation, reshaped the dimension of technological art in technological development, and helped technology evolve toward life itself. The fifth aspect, practical skills, emphasized the practical skills and application skills of engineering students to better apply engineering knowledge and tools to real engineering problems (Gu, 2017; Ye, Kong, & Zhang, 2018). As a result, the reform of the New Engineering Education development strategy included objective, targeted, and systematic training of engineering talent and clear direction.

Table 4 Talent Cultivation Ability of New Engineering Education

Dimension of Ability Required for Engineering Talent	Competency Category	Concrete Ability
De (Morality)	Spirit of engineering ethics	Professional ethics and social responsibility consciousness Humanistic and social accomplishments Spirit of engineering innovation
Zhi (Intelligence)	Professional basic ability	Basic theoretical capacity Professional and technical capacity Interdisciplinary thinking ability Inter-university integration capacity Systematic thinking ability
Ti (Physique)	Sustainable competitiveness	Adaptability to change Lifelong learning ability
Mei (Creativity)	Innovative design ability	Engineering design capability Computational thinking Critical thinking and analytical ability
Lao (Practice)	Practical ability	Engineering practice capability Ability to use tools Ability to learn and apply Engineering leadership

Source: Based on studies by Lin (2018), Xu et al. (2017), Lu et al. (2017), Ye et al. (2018), and Gu (2017).

Situation of the Development of New Engineering Education

According to the statistical analysis of the current literatures, the situation of the development of New Engineering Education mainly focused on two levels: one is teaching level and the other is education system level (as shown in Table 5).

Table 5 Scope of Research Content for New Engineering Education

Situation of the development of New Engineering Education	Number of articles
Education and teaching level	132
Education system level	71

Source: Compiled by the author.

Research at the Level of Teaching

The first aspect was to grasp the professional logic and reconstruct the curriculum content system. The development of New Engineering Education required the construction of a new knowledge system. The traditional knowledge system for engineering talent mainly consisted of public courses, professional basic courses, and professional courses, which could not meet the challenges of the new industrial revolution nor those of the national strategies of Made in China 2025 and Innovation-driven Development (Zhu & Li, 2018). Therefore, to promote the development of New Engineering Education, it was necessary to update the professional training program(Lin, 2017a; Ren et al., 2019), to reconstruct the curriculum system to meet new requirements in terms of knowledge content and skills, and to design a new curriculum and teaching content accordingly. **The second aspect was to integrate cutting-edge technologies and explore diverse teaching modes.** With the continuous integration of modern information technology and the Internet Plus environment, teaching methods for engineering talent training have undergone fundamental changes (Zhu&Li, 2018). Therefore, it was necessary to adjust teaching methods according to the interests of the students, to improve teaching efficiency and effectiveness, and to promote the reform of teaching methods. **The third aspect was to reform assessments and build an engineering innovation platform.** First, thanks to the reform of the evaluation system, engineering education could return to engineering (Ye et al., 2019; Zhong, 2017). Second, the creation of an engineering innovation platform integrating education, training, and research and development (Yang, Chen & Dong, 2019)should increase interdisciplinary professional cooperation in schools, expand out-of-school collaboration with Governments, Industries, Universities, Institutes, and stress the importance of international cooperation to train engineering talent, develop research and development in industrial technology, and serve regional economic development (Lin, 2017a).

Research at the Level of the Education System

In addition to achieving breakthroughs in the development of New Engineering Education at the level of education and teaching, current research has also focused on the education system, considering the introduction or design of the overall framework, to promote the development of New Engineering Education, as shown in Table 6.

Table 6 Research at the Level of the Education System in New Engineering Education

Education system level	Concrete development in New Engineering Education
CDIO conversion platform	Based on the analysis of the construction elements of the CDIO conversion platform used as a practice path, the platform embodied systematic thinking, educational environment, training modes, and innovative practices in engineering education
Excellent Program 2.0	According to the general idea of the Excellent Program 2.0, industry enterprises are deeply involved in the training process, universities cultivate engineering talent based on general standards and industry standards, and strengthen the engineering and innovation capabilities of students

Source: Compiled by the author.

The first aspect was to build the CDIO conversion platform at the system level. CDIO, an innovative educational model, aims to train the next generation of leaders in the field of engineering. It focuses on engineering theory and engineering practice in real-world systems and the product process of Conceive, Design, Implement, and Operate. This includes systematic thinking, educational environment, training modes, and innovative practice in engineering education, which are of great importance to the practice path of New Engineering Education. Ye et al. (2018) believed that the CDIO model based on the system life cycle embodied the essential characteristics of engineering, different from those of science. For New Engineering Education, the knowledge and lessons learned from its practice path could be discussed by analyzing the construction and environmental elements of the CDIO conversion platform (Ye, Kong, & Zhang, 2018). Based on grounded theory, Ye Min et al. (2018) summarized the relevant elements of the CDIO conversion platform into five platform components, “curriculum setting, teacher policy, academic evaluation, teaching methods, and university culture,” and three environmental support elements, “national strategy, financial support, and industry participation.” **The second aspect was to promote the Excellence Program 2.0 at the system level.** To improve the quality of engineering education and accelerate China’s progress toward becoming a strong country in engineering education, China launched the “Excellent Engineer Training Program” (hereinafter the “Excellent Program”) in 2010. In June 2017, Lin Huiqing, Vice Minister of Education, pointed out that “colleges and universities should take the initiative to serve the needs of national strategy and industrial enterprises, accelerate the construction and development of New Engineering Education, and create an upgraded version of the ‘Excellence Program.’” From a design perspective, the Excellent Program focused on three main characteristics that could be used to develop New Engineering Education: industry enterprises are deeply involved in the training process; universities cultivate engineering talent based on general standards and industry standards; and universities strengthen students’ engineering and innovation capabilities. Lin Jian (2017a) proposed that as an improved version of the Excellent Program, the development of New

Engineering Education should include research and practice related to aspects of education and teaching, discipline and professional structures, discipline and professional development, talent training modes, multi-party cooperation, practice and innovation platform, teaching staff construction, and talent training quality, by adjusting the ideas of discipline and professional development and reinforcing the importance of the reform of engineering education. Zhu et al. (2018) believed that the main ideas of the Excellent Program 2.0 included support for the development strategy of engineering education in China in the new era. As a result, it was necessary to actively explore and implement the paradigm of “integration and innovation,” the construction of a new knowledge system, the management methods of the professional environment, the modes of talent training, and the diversification of teaching methods (Zhu & Li, 2018).

Discussion

Based on the current literature and considering the characteristics, limitations, and weaknesses of traditional engineering education research, this study proposed a systematic logical framework for the development of New Engineering Education, including policy logic, the logic of industrial demand, the logic of disciplinary evolution and the logic of knowledge derivation. This helped to explain how engineering education had evolved in the face of the Fourth Industrial Revolution and market demand and to find a possible breakthrough to promote the paradigm shift in engineering education.

Policy Logic in the Development of New Engineering Education—Chinese Characteristics

Most of the major reforms in higher education in China were driven by national policies based on economic and social needs, while the development of New Engineering Education had clear characteristics of economic, technological, and industrial development. General Secretary Xi Jinping pointed out, “our need for higher education is more urgent than ever, and our thirst for scientific knowledge and outstanding talent is more intense than ever.”² Following the proposal of New Engineering Education, industrial policies at the national level included the content of the development of New Engineering Education and new engineering talent training (as shown in Table 7), which became an important policy logic to promote the development of engineering education and the creation and training of engineering talent in New Engineering Education.

² http://www.gov.cn/xinwen/2016-12/08/content_5145253.htm?allContent#1

Table 7 Summary of Talent Policy Documents in New Engineering Education

Date	Issue agency	Policy name	Core content
Feb 18, 2017	MOE	Symposium on the Strategy of Developing Higher Engineering Education (Fudan Consensus)	The path choice for the construction and development of New Engineering Education was that universities play a leading and supporting role, with strong support from the government and social forces
Feb 24, 2017	MOE MOHRSS	Guidelines for the Development Planning of Manufacturing Talent	Five key talent projects were proposed, and the innovative talent development system and mechanism should be improved to further improve the quality of the manufacturing talent team
Apr 8, 2017	MOE	Symposium on New Engineering Education Construction(Tianjin University Action Plan)	The specific modes and methods of talent cultivation in New Engineering Education were discussed in depth, and 9 main tasks, 10 key areas, and 5 major projects were proposed
Jun 9, 2017	MOE	Guidelines for New Engineering Education Construction (Beijing Guidelines)	Continue to deepen the reform of engineering education, train high-quality engineering talent, and explore the possibility of creating an engineering education system with Chinese characteristics and global standards
Jul 20, 2017	General Office of the State Council, PRC	Next Generation Artificial Intelligence Development Plan	Support and train leading talent in artificial intelligence with development potential, promote compound talent training, and focus on vertical compound talent training and horizontal compound talent training
Dec 19, 2017	General Office of the State Council, PRC	Deepening the Integration of Industry and Education	Emphasize the development pattern of the integration of education and industry as a whole, deepen the integration of industry and education, and promote the organic connection of the education chain, the talent chain, the industrial chain, and the innovation chain
Mar 21, 2018	MOE	Announcement of the First Batch of "New Engineering" Research and Practice Projects	The first batch of 612 national "new engineering" research and practice projects was identified, covering 19 project groups, including popular "New Engineering" topics such as artificial intelligence, big data, and intelligent manufacturing
Apr 11, 2018	MOE	AI Innovation Action Plan for Colleges and Universities	Promote the cross-integration of discipline and specialty education and create a new model of composite specialty education: "artificial intelligence + X". By 2020, 100 "AI +X" composite specialties will be built and 50 AI institutes, research institutes or cross-disciplinary research centers will be established
Oct 08, 2018	MOE MOI CAE	Opinions on Accelerating the Construction and Development of New Engineering and Implementing the Excellent Engineer Education and Training Plan 2.0	Focus on building a series of new high-level universities in science and engineering and multi-agent institutes to develop the industry and meet the future needs of emerging engineering institutes of technology, industry professionals, and the new curriculum; Cultivate the engineering practice skills of high-level professional teachers, representing more than 20% of the engineering professionals, through international equivalent professional certifications
Dec 08, 2018	NDRC MOST MOE	The Initiative to Strengthen Collaborative Innovation Between Education and the Science and Technology Innovation Platform and Promote the Integration of Science and Education	Emphasize the deep integration of artificial intelligence, big data, virtual reality, and other technologies with education, promote the integration of science and education, and explore new avenues for collaborative innovation and the development of industry and education and scientific research
Apr 03, 2019	NDRC MOE	Implementation Measures for the Construction of Enterprises Integrating Production and Education (Trial)	Promote a deep fusion between the demand side and the supply side; Teach integrated production enterprise construction as an important direction for the construction of a modern enterprise system; Promote "policy mix"; Motivate companies to participate in the reform of the integration of production and education through the talent cultivation system, the science and technology innovation chain of supply and demand, and the tens of thousands of fusion companies supporting the development of high quality "learning factories" created to accelerate talent acquisition for structural reforms

Source: Compiled by the author.

Therefore, this study showed that in the current situation in China, national policies have strongly dominated and supported the reform and development of engineering education in China, providing a clear vision of the planning and construction logic of New Engineering Education and high-level design and guiding ideas for theoretical innovation, system innovation, and practical innovation in engineering education with Chinese characteristics.

The Logic of Industrial Demand for the Development of New Engineering Education—Engineering Essence

Practice is an essential attribute of engineering(Wang, 2015), and its goal is to cultivate talent for industrial development to meet the needs of the industry(Zhu,Zhou,&Li, 2017). Given the historical process of paradigm shift in engineering education, it has been found that the essential attribute of engineering and the complex changes in the environment of the engineering system and their interactions have determined the evolution of the engineering education paradigm. Therefore, the emergence and development of the industrial revolution can also be seen as a process in which the development values and modes of engineering and engineering education have evolved(Qiu,Li,&Wu, 2014). As a result, some scholars have begun to reflect on the construction logic of New Engineering Education in terms of talent demand in the global industrial reform, suggesting that the novelty of New Engineering Education was based on the industry's new demand for engineering talent and the understanding and responding to the new modes of future formats. It emphasized the guiding role of new

talent demand formats to promote the revolution of traditional concepts in engineering education, the curriculum system, and the education system(Ye&Qian, 2017).

Table 8 Analysis of the Trend of Industrial Change and Paradigm Shift in Engineering Education

Industrial revolution	First industrial revolution	Second industrial revolution	Third industrial revolution	Fourth industrial revolution
Characteristics of the industrial reform	Represented by steam engine technology The era of steam technology	Represented by internal combustion engine and electric power technology The era of electrical technology	Represented by computers and information technology The era of information technology	Represented by artificial intelligence, quantum technology, etc. The era of new technologies
	Mechanization	Mechanization	<u>Informatization</u>	<u>Intelligentization</u>
	Simple production in factories	Technological scale production	Integration of science and technology	Integration of politics, economics, science and technology, etc.
	Engineering education paradigm	Technological paradigm	Scientific paradigm	Engineering paradigm
Characteristics of engineering education	Education mode: apprenticeship	Education mode: scientific training mode	Education mode: open, practice-oriented, and comprehensive engineering education mode
	Training direction: craftsmen (field engineers)	Training direction: engineering scientists	Training direction: engineers
	Learning content: discipline and curriculum system of handicraft technology, academic engineering education gradually developed at a later stage	Learning content: theory of engineering science, laboratory development and research, and discussion of theoretical issues	Learning content: engineering practices, technology and scientific theory, returning to engineering practices and starting from practical problems

Source: Compiled by the authors.

Therefore, this study showed that the logic of industrial demand was important in the development of New Engineering Education. In addition, it emphasized that the development of New Engineering Education should further explore the characteristics of industrial demand with Chinese characteristics and the attributes of engineering education and continuously optimize the knowledge system, level types, and capability structure of engineering talent, to comply with the ever-changing global technological reform and the sustainable development of the industry in China (as shown in Table 8).

The Logic of Disciplinary Evolution in the Development of New Engineering Education—Discipline Development

When the knowledge system is completely inherited, taught, and innovated, a discipline is represented as an academic system, a knowledge organization, a teaching subject, or a form of activity (Zhou&Wu, 2016). Therefore, we believe that the construction and development of disciplines have their own unique evolutionary logic. Metzger (1987) proposed four paradigms of disciplinary evolution in the United States based on the early history of disciplinary evolution in higher education in the United States, namely Subject Parturition, Subject Dignification, Subject Dispersion, and Program Affiliation. From the perspective of the global paradigm shift in engineering education, the entanglement of science and technology was a unique attribute of the construction and development of engineering disciplines in the period of the

technological paradigm, the scientific paradigm, and the engineering paradigm. Recently, some scholars have also begun to explore the construction and development of New Engineering Education from the evolution of the discipline itself. This study summarized the approach in two logics: the logic of disciplinary evolution and the logic of disciplinary derivation.

The first logic is the logic of disciplinary evolution. Compared with traditional engineering, New Engineering Education is a more dynamic concept (Wu et al., 2017). Its development cannot be completely separated from traditional engineering, but is the product of transformation and upgrading based on traditional engineering. Liu et al. (2019) believed that New Engineering Education did not mean completely breaking away from traditional engineering. On the contrary, New Engineering Education was closely related to traditional engineering. There should be no absolute boundary between “old engineering” and New Engineering Education. Indeed, the “new” and the “old” are always relative, dynamic, and developing. The construction of New Engineering Education should keep pace with the times and beat the forefront of progress. Similarly, Li et al. (2017) proposed that New Engineering Education should not abandon traditional engineering because of its “novelty”, but should create a new form of engineering integrity through “traditional engineering+.”

The second logic is the logic of disciplinary derivation. Consistent with the connotation of Subject Parturition, New Engineering Education is a new discipline created by the cross-combination of different engineering disciplines or the cross-integration of engineering disciplines and other disciplines. On the other hand, disciplines and specialties for the development of new technologies and industries in the future will be nurtured, expanded, and developed from other non-engineering disciplines, especially basic disciplines such as applied science (Lin, 2017a).

The Logic of Knowledge Derivation in the Development of New Engineering Education—Education Essence

Starting from the evolution process of engineering education and research and practice in New Engineering Education, we examined three types of logic in the construction of New Engineering Education, policy logic, industrial logic, and the logic of discipline, highlighting the importance of New Engineering Education from different perspectives and pointing out the directions for the development of New Engineering Education. At the same time, it was worth noting that the rapid growth and evolution of the current industry and the constant change and innovation of knowledge forced us to think about the unique derivative logic of the production, specialization, systematization, dissemination, and absorption of current and future knowledge.

Based on the continuous analysis of disciplines in the development of New Engineering Education and industrial logic, we found that the development of New Engineering Education was based on the reform of education and that the main logic of education was “the logic of knowledge.” With the arrival of the fourth revolution of science and technology and the continuous progress of human society, the degree of integration of various situations and factors, such as crowds, social economy, technology, and culture, is deepening, and the way of producing knowledge is also evolving (Wang,Li,&Xiang, 2018). As knowledge creation evolves to meet the new demand for industrial development, the traditional knowledge system can no longer cope with current development and innovation, and reform is urgently needed. In the development of New Engineering Education, we should pay attention to the most essential logic of knowledge, answer the questions of knowledge production, specialization, systematization, dissemination, and absorption, and discuss and analyze the general laws of knowledge evolution and development to achieve the lowest logical construction of New Engineering Education.

Figure 4: Logical Architecture of the New Engineering Education Development System

Source: Drawn by the author.

Based on the above logical analysis of the development of New Engineering Education, **we found that “policy logic, industrial logic, the logic of discipline, and the logic of knowledge” have the unity of systematic logic and answer the eternal question of the process of education: the matching of “supply and demand” in talent cultivation.** Whether the engineering talent cultivated by universities can meet the

needs of society has become the cornerstone of the development of New Engineering Education.

Conclusion

Based on 260 academic papers on the theme “New Engineering Education” from January 2017 to June 2019, this study proposed a preliminary analysis of the current state of research in New Engineering Education. First, this study used the systematic review method to provide a comprehensive and systematic summary of the results of current research in New Engineering Education based on the following five aspects: (motivation)Why, (subject)Who, (objective)What, (situation)Where, and (logic)How. Second, in terms of motivations for the development of New Engineering Education, the background section of the study proposed that the development of New Engineering Education was the result of multi-level and multi-factor promotion and that these motivations were further divided into the factors of policy level, industry level, and engineering education level. Third, with respect to the subjects of the development of New Engineering Education, based on current research, this study proposed to further specify the characteristics and regional attributes of the different subjects of the development of New Engineering Education to develop New Engineering Education in terms of layers and categories. Fourth, with regard to the objectives of developing New Engineering Education, this study systematically sorted out the development of disciplines and ability training and innovatively classified the remaining skills of talent training in New Engineering Education in the literature into professional basic ability, practical skills, systematic thinking ability, engineering innovation capacity, and active learning ability. Fifth, based on current research, this study proposed four main types of logic in the development of New Engineering Education, namely policy logic, the logic of industrial demand, the logic of disciplinary evolution, and the logic of knowledge derivation, which helped to explain how engineering education has evolved in the face of the industrial revolution and market demand and to find a possible breakthrough to promote the paradigm shift in engineering education. Sixth, this study not only sorted out and analyzed the above five aspects in isolation, but integrated their logical relationships to construct a research and analysis framework for the development of New Engineering Education, taking into account the integrity and micro-logicality of research. These five aspects presented some logical relationships: (1) the subjects of the development of New Engineering Education had different motivations, logic types, and target effects based on their own attributes; and (2) under different motivations, the results of using different types of logic were the objectives of the development of New Engineering Education. Finally, the whole process took place in a specific situation, which affected and restricted it. The New Engineering Education research framework based on these logical relationships is illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: The New Engineering Education Research Framework

Source: Drawn by the author.

Limitations and Prospects

According to the research framework presented above, this study suggests that there is room for further in-depth research on the development of New Engineering Education, from the perspective of research, to deepen research content, or from the perspective of measurement and quantification results. **First, from the perspective of research**, current research has focused on macro-industrial logic and policy logic, preferring the analysis of education teaching and teaching systems, while few studies have discussed disciplinary evolution at the micro level and knowledge derivation. Future research should focus on these aspects to deepen and refine New Engineering Education’s research and practice from amore evolutionary perspective at the micro level, such as strengthening the identification of construction subject attributes for New Engineering Education, analyzing the characteristics of construction situations, and exploring how different types of subjects rely on the logic of disciplinary evolution and the logic of knowledge derivation to develop New Engineering Education. **Second, in terms of research content**, the development of New Engineering Education should be a systematic project of higher education and teaching reform. Current research and practice have focused on the combination of different types of motivations, subjects, logic, goals, and situations for the development of New Engineering Education. Few researches have comprehensively considered the systematism of these factors. Future research should classify and compare the development paths of New Engineering Education based on the logical framework of the construction system of New Engineering Education, conduct in-depth research on various types of construction processes in New Engineering Education, and provide information on how to better promote the construction and development of New

Engineering Education, create an engineering education paradigm with Chinese characteristics, and develop an engineering education theoretical system with Chinese characteristics. **Third, in terms of research methods**, current research has mainly focused on theoretical research, supplemented by case studies, with only a small number of empirical studies and a lack of interactive verification of different methods. Future research on New Engineering Education should pay more attention to the comprehensiveness and diversity of research methods. The research methods of vertical co-performance, grounded theory, or the fs/QCA software, for instance, can be used to compare various types of New Engineering Education construction paths, providing useful information. **Fourth, in terms of measurement and quantification results**, current research has been rather vague in judging the developmental effects of New Engineering Education, with almost no mature concepts, dimensions, and items, and even less quantitative indicators. How many and what types of construction subjects are needed for the development of a new engineering practice project? How long will it take to train engineering talent for a new project? How to evaluate the effectiveness of talent training? No current research has answered these questions. Therefore, it is suggested that research on these issues may provide detailed information on the breadth, depth, and duration of New Engineering Education.

REFERENCES

- [1] 2017a. "New Engineering Education" Construction, Fudan Consensus. Research in Higher Education of Engineering1: 10-11.
- [2] 2017b. "New Engineering Education" Construction, Action Line (Tianjin University Action Plan). Research in Higher Education of Engineering2: 24-25.
- [3] BORREGO, Maura, FOSTER, Margaret J., & FROYD, Jeffrey E. 2014. Systematic Literature Reviews in Engineering Education and Other Developing Interdisciplinary Fields. Journal of Engineering Education103(1): 45-76.
- [4] CHEN, Hui, & CHEN, Min. 2017. Reflections and Explorations on the Training of New Engineering Talents in Comprehensive Universities. Research in Higher Education of Engineering2: 19-23.
- [5] GONG, Wei, ZHOU, Kai, ZHU, Guang-ya, et al. 2018. Exploration on the Design of a CLT-based Comprehensive Experiment on Power Electronics for New Engineering. Experimental Technology and Management4: 177-179.

- [6] GU, Pei-hua. 2017. The Concept, Framework and Implementation Approaches of New Engineering Education(3E) and the New Paradigm. Research in Higher Education of Engineering 6: 1-13.
- [7] GU, Pei-hua, HU, Wen-long, LU, Xiao-hua, et al. 2017. From CDIO in China to China's CDIO: Study on Development Path, Impacts and Causes. Research in Higher Education of Engineering 1: 24-43.
- [8] GU, Tian-long, &WEI, Yin-xia. 2018. Encouraging Local Universities to Build First-class Undergraduate Education based on the Concept of New Engineering Education. China University Teaching 2: 32-35.
- [9] HU, Bo, FENG, Hui, HAN, Wei-li, & XU, Lei. 2017. Accelerating the Establishment of New Engineering and Technical Disciplines and Promoting Innovation in Engineering Education: A Review of the Symposium on the Strategy for the Development of Higher Engineering Education. Fudan Education Forum 2: 20-27.
- [10] HUANG, Yan, TIAN, Wei-xia, XIA, Chen-fei, et al. 2019. Facing the Reform and Practice of "Electronic Information +" in the New Engineering Talent Training Mode. China University Teaching 1: 44-47.
- [11] JESSON, Jill K., MATHESON, Lydia, & LACEY, Fiona M. 2011. Doing Your Literature Review: Traditional and Systematic Techniques. London: SAGE Publications.
- [12] JIN, Xin, LI, Liang-jun, DU, Jing, LIU, Jing, & ZHONG, De-ming. 2018. Construction of the Curriculum System of Mechanical Foundation in the Context of New Engineering. Journal of Machine Design 35(S2): 114-118.
- [13] LI, Hua, HU, Na, & YOU, Zhen-sheng. 2017. New Engineering Education: Form, Connotation and Directions. Research in Higher Education of Engineering 4: 16-19.
- [14] LI, Man-li. 2010. An Inquiry into Engineers and Engineering Education. Shanghai: The Commercial Press.
- [15] LI, Pei-gen. 2017. What's New for New Engineering Education. Research in Higher Education of Engineering 4: 1-4.
- [16] LI, Xiu-juan, ZHANG, Zhi-hui, ZOU, Meng, et al. 2019. Analysis of the Need to Establish a New Bionics Discipline and Program from the Perspective of Demand. Research in Higher Education of Engineering 2: 46-49.

- [17] LIN, Jian. 2017a. New Engineering Education Construction: An Updated Version of “The Plan for Educating and Training Outstanding Engineers” with a Sustained Effort. Research in Higher Education of Engineering3: 7-14.
- [18] LIN, Jian. 2017b. The Construction of China’s New Engineering Disciplines for the Future. Tsinghua Journal of Education2: 26-35.
- [19] LIN, Jian. 2018. The Transformation and Upgrading of Traditional Engineering Programs under the Wave of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. Research in Higher Education of Engineering4: 1-10.
- [20] LIN, Jian, & HU, De-xin. 2018. Comparison and Reference of the Reform Experience of International Engineering Education – Based on the Examples of the United States, Great Britain, Germany and France. Research in Higher Education of Engineering2: 96-110.
- [21] LIN, Jian, & ZHENG, Li-na. 2018. From a Large Country to a Strong One: China’s Engineering Education in the 40 Years of Reform and Opening-up. Tsinghua Journal of Education2: 1-17.
- [22] LIU, Wei-Dong, XIONG, Yang, & Zhang, Dan-ping. 2019. Quality Analysis and Evaluation of the Construction of New Engineering Education Based on the Process Factor Model. Research in Higher Education of Engineering1: 34-40.
- [23] LIU, Ji-zhen, ZHAI, Ya-jun, & XUN, Zhen-fang. Analysis of the Connotation of Emerging Engineering Education and Its Construction. Research in Higher Education of Engineering3: 21-28.
- [24] LU, Guo-dong. 2017. Five Breakthroughs and Preliminary Explorations in the Construction of “New Engineering Education.” China University Teaching 5: 38-41.
- [25] LU, Guo-dong, & LI, Tuo-yu. 2017. Reflections on the Ways of Constructing and Developing New Engineering Education. Research in Higher Education of Engineering3: 20-26.
- [26] LU, Zheng, & SHANG GUAN, Yu-qi. 2018. Research on the Talent Training of New Engineering Education Based on the Undergraduate Tutorial System: Taking the College of Civil Engineering, Tongji University, as an Example. Journal of Architectural Education in Institutions of Higher Learning2: 1-4.
- [27] MAO, Jiang-hua, & DAI, Xin. 2019. influencing the participation of engineering students in science and technology competitions. Research in Higher Education

of Engineering3: 52-56.

- [28] METZGER, Walter P. 1987. The Academic Profession in the United States. In CLARK, Burton R. (Ed.), *The Academic Profession: National, Disciplinary, and Institutional Settings*(pp. 123-208).Berkeley: University of California Press.
- [29] NI, Wei-chuan, LI, Jia, WANG, Feng, et al. 2018. Construction of an Application-oriented Fab Lab Experimental Platform for Undergraduate Students in the Context of New Engineering. Experimental Technology and Management1: 269-272.
- [30] QIAO, Xu. 2018. Original Aspiration, Ingenuity and Ambition –For the Transformation and Development of the Chemical Industry, Nanjing Tech University’s Dream and Action. China University Teaching2: 27-31.
- [31] QIN, Wei-wei, &WANG, Sui-dong. 2018. The Innovative Pathway of New Engineering Education – A Case Study of Talent Cultivation in Nanoscience and Technology at Soochow University. Journal of Higher Education2: 79-84.
- [32] QIU, Xue-qing, LI, Zheng, &WU, Ying-liang. 2014. The Reform of Engineering Education Oriented Towards the New Industrial Revolution. Research in Higher Education of Engineering5: 5-14.
- [33] REYNOLDS, Terry S., &SEELY, Bruce E. 1993. Striving for Balance: A Hundred Years of the American Society for Engineering Education. Journal of Engineering Education 82(3): 136-151.
- [34] REN, Yu-zhuo, XU, Lin-mei, XIE, Xiao-mei, et al. 2019. Design and Practice of the Training Program and Innovative Curriculum for Emerging Engineering Majors. Research in Higher Education of Engineering3: 29-32+46.
- [35] SHI, Da-ning, &LIANG, Wen-ping. 2018. Reflections and Explorations on the Construction of New Engineering Education with Aeronautics and Astronautics Characteristics.China University Teaching9: 26-28.
- [36] SONG, Yu-qing, CHEN,, Zhe, et al. 2018. Research and Practice in International Engineering Innovative Talent Cultivation for New Engineering Education: Based on Cross-team Experience and Blended Learning Model. Journal of Higher Education Management3: 102-108.
- [37] SUN, Ke-xue, GUO, Yu-feng, XIAO, Jian, et al. 2018. Construction and Exploration of the Engineering Practical Teaching System for New Engineering. Experimental Technology and Management5: 233-235.

- [38] Wall K. 2010. Engineering: Issues, Challenges and Opportunities for Development.
- [39] WANG, De-ming. 2017. The Construction of “New Engineering” Specialty and Academy Education in the Mining Industry – Exclusive Interview with Professor WANG De-ming. A Famous Scientist in Coal Science. Meitan Higher Education3: 1-3.
- [40] WANG, Pei-liang, LI, Bing, WANG, Rong-de, et al. 2018. Exploring Talent Cultivation in New Engineering Education– Based on the Perspective of Building a Collaborative Innovation Center. Chinese University Science & Technology3: 45-47.
- [41] WANG, Pei-min. 2013. Engineering Education Research in China: Decline and Revival. Research in Higher Education of Engineering6: 13-21.
- [42] WANG, Pei-min. 2015. Fundamentals of Engineering Education – Research on the Concept and Practice of Engineering Education. Higher Education Press. China,
- [43] WANG, Ying-jun, LI, Zheng, & XIANG, Cong. 2018. Reform of the Engineering Talent Training Mode Based on "4I." Research in Higher Education of Engineering2: 15-19.
- [44] WEI, Jiang, LI, Tuo-yu, & ZHAO, Yu-han. 2015. Innovation-driven Development: Current Situation, Realistic Difficult Position and Countermeasures. China Soft Science5: 21-30.
- [45] WU, Ai-hua, HOU, Yong-feng, YANG, Qiu-bo, & HAO, Jie. 2017. Accelerating the Development and Construction of New Engineering, Taking the Initiative to Adapt and Lead the New. Research in Higher Education of Engineering1: 1-9.
- [46] XU, Jun, WANG, Ziqiang, & SHI, Yi. 2017. On Constructing New Engineering Education for Future Industry Transformation and Talent Cultivation: A Case Study of the Microelectronics Industry. Research in Higher Education of Engineering2: 13-18.
- [47] XU, Lei, HU, Bo, FENG, Hui, & HAN, Wei-li. 2017. Reflections on New Engineering Education in Comprehensive Universities. Research in Higher Education of Engineering2: 6-12.
- [48] XU, Xiao-fei, & DING, Xiao-hua. 2017. Exploring the Reform of Talent Training in New Engineering Education in the Face of Sustainable Competitiveness.

China University Teaching6: 6-10.

- [49] YANG, Bing. 2017. Construction of New Engineering Education: Version and Action – Taking Tsinghua University as an example, Tianjin: Tianjin University.
- [50] YANG, Guo-fu, & YU Min-jie. 2019. International Comparison of the Interdisciplinary Construction under the Background of Emerging Engineering Education. Research in Higher Education of Engineering3: 57-61+86.
- [51] YANG, Nan-yue, & LI, Zheng-ming. 2019. Construction of a Virtual Training Laboratory for Innovation Practice in New Engineering Based on “VR+.” Experimental Technology and Management 36(1): 130-133.
- [52] YANG, Zu-xing, CHEN, Yan, & DONG, Li-ping. 2019. Construction of an Intensive Training System for Advanced Manufacturing Technology in an Engineering Training Center. Experimental Technology and Management 36(2): 186-189.
- [53] YE, Min, KONG, Han-bing, & ZHANG, Wei. 2018. New Engineering Education: From Idea to Action. Research in Higher Education of Engineering 1: 24-31.
- [54] YE, Min, LI, Tuo-yu, DENG, Yong-xin, & ZHU, Ling. 2019. The Frontier of Future Engineering Education: Based on Past and Present Progress. Research in Higher Education of Engineering 2: 26-32.
- [55] YE, Min, & QIAN, Hui. 2017. Originality in New Types of Industries and New Engineering Education. Research in Higher Education of Engineering4: 5-9.
- [56] YE, Min, SUN, Han-bing, & XU, Xing. 2018. Exploring the Practical Paths of New Engineering Education: Construction of the CDIO Conversion Platform Based on Grounded Theory. Research in Higher Education of Engineering4: 11-17.
- [57] ZHANG, Gan-qing, GUO, Lei, & XIANG, Yang-hui. 2018. Practical Teaching Paradigm of Innovative Entrepreneurial Talent Cultivation in New Engineering Education. Higher Education Exploration8: 55-60.
- [58] ZHENG, Qing-hua. 2017. Creating a "New Engineering" Education Model under the Guidance of Innovation and Entrepreneurship Education. China University Teaching12: 8-12.
- [59] ZHENG, Quan-shui. 2018. Curriculum Structure for Innovative Engineering Education. Mechanics in Engineering2: 194-202.
- [60] ZHONG, Deng-hua. 2017. Connotations and Actions for the Establishment of

New Engineering Education. Research in Higher Education of Engineering3: 1-6.

- [61] ZHOU, Guang-li, &WU, Jian-xin. 2016. What is aWorldClass Discipline?China Higher Education Research1: 65-73.
- [62] ZHU, Zheng-wei, &LI, Mao-guo. 2018. Reflections on the Implementation of the Education and Training Plan for Outstanding Engineers 2.0. Research in Higher Education of Engineering 1: 46-53.
- [63] ZHU, Zheng-wei, ZHOU, Hong-fang, &LI, Mao-guo. 2017. “New Engineering” Aimed atthe New Industrial System. Chongqing Higher Education Research3: 15-21.